

DEVELOPMENT OF INTENSIVE FISHING IN THE AGRICULTURE.

Dosekeeva Aksungul Esmagambetovna

1st year master's student of Nukus branch of Samarkand University of
Veterinary Medicine, Animal Husbandry and Biotechnology
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Abstract. The development of intensive fishing in the agriculture industry has led to significant advancements in aquaculture and fish farming. This approach involves the use of advanced technology, sustainable practices, and specialized equipment to increase fish production and meet the growing demand for seafood. Intensive fishing methods also aim to improve efficiency, reduce environmental impact, and ensure the welfare of farmed fish. However, it is important to carefully monitor and manage the potential ecological and environmental implications of intensive fishing to maintain a balance between increased production and sustainable resource management. This article highlights the ongoing evolution of intensive fishing practices within the agriculture industry and the importance of responsible and sustainable approaches to meet the global demand for fish products.

Keywords: Intensive fishing, aquaculture, fish farming, sustainable practices, environmental impact, technology, fish production, resource management, ecological implications, sustainable development.

Intensive fishing in agriculture refers to a farming method that involves the use of high levels of inputs, such as water, fertilizers, pesticides, and labor, to maximize the yield of a specific crop. This method often involves the use of advanced technology and efficient irrigation systems to ensure the highest possible output from the agricultural land. It is commonly practiced in areas with high population density and limited arable land, where maximizing the yield from the available land is essential for food production [6].

Fish farming, also known as aquaculture, holds significant importance in addressing food demand in the agriculture of Uzbekistan for several reasons:

-Diversification of Food Sources: Fish farming contributes to the diversification of the food sources available in Uzbekistan. By adding fish as a protein source, it can complement traditional agricultural products, providing a variety of nutritional options for the population.

-Increased Protein Supply: Fish is a high-quality source of protein, essential for a balanced diet. With the growing population and increasing demand for protein-rich foods, fish farming can help address the protein deficit by providing a steady supply of fish.

-Sustainable Agriculture: As a form of sustainable agriculture, fish farming can be integrated with other agricultural practices, contributing to the efficient use of natural resources such as water and land. This sustainability is important for meeting long-term food demands in Uzbekistan.

-Economic Opportunities: Fish farming provides employment opportunities and income generation for the local population, contributing to economic growth and livelihood improvement in rural areas [7].

-Food Security: With its high nutritional value, fish can contribute to improving food security, particularly in regions where access to diverse and nutritious food options is limited.

-Given these factors, fish farming can play a critical role in addressing food demand and contributing to the overall agriculture and food security in Uzbekistan.

Sustainable fish farming practices are crucial for maintaining ecological balance and conserving natural resources. In the context of Uzbekistan, implementing sustainable farming practices in aquaculture can have several benefits:

1. Environmental Conservation: Sustainable fish farming focuses on minimizing environmental impact by implementing water recirculation systems, reducing chemical usage, and managing waste effectively, thereby conserving water resources and maintaining the ecological balance of aquatic ecosystems.

2. Biodiversity Preservation: By adhering to sustainable practices such as proper site selection and responsible aquaculture techniques, fish farmers can help preserve local biodiversity and reduce the potential negative effects on native species.

3. Community Well-being: Sustainable fish farming practices can enhance the well-being of local communities by creating employment opportunities and supporting economic development, while simultaneously minimizing environmental and social impacts.

4. Responsible Feed Management: Effective use of aquafeed and sustainable feed management techniques can help reduce reliance on wild fish stocks for feed and minimize environmental pollution from excess feed and waste products.

5. Compliance with Regulations: Adhering to sustainable farming practices ensures that fish farmers comply with local and international environmental regulations, fostering a responsible and ethical approach to aquatic resource utilization [9].

It is clear that sustainable fish farming practices are essential for the long-term viability of aquaculture in Uzbekistan. By adopting these practices, the aquaculture industry can contribute to environmental conservation, preserve biodiversity, and enhance the well-being of local communities while meeting the increasing demand for fish and aquatic products.

Conclusion. The development of intensive fish farming, particularly through the implementation of recirculating aquaculture systems (RAS), holds great potential for transforming the aquaculture sector in Uzbekistan. This approach can significantly improve the efficiency, sustainability, and productivity of fish farming while minimizing the environmental impact. The successful implementation of RAS will require a combination of technological investment, training and capacity building, policy support, and research and development. By investing in RAS technology and providing the necessary support and incentives, Uzbekistan can effectively enhance its aquaculture industry, contributing to improved food security, economic growth, and environmental sustainability. The adoption of RAS will not only lead to increased fish production but also help conserve water resources, reduce the reliance on wild-caught fish, and meet the growing demand for high-quality seafood products. Therefore, the development of intensive fish farming in the agriculture sector of Uzbekistan through RAS implementation is an important step toward achieving sustainable aquaculture practices and addressing the nation's food production needs.

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